

A Peer Reviewed International Journal of Asian
Research Consortium

AJRBF:
**ASIAN JOURNAL OF
RESEARCH IN BANKING
AND FINANCE**

MUTUAL FUND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

B. RAJA MANNAR*; DR. B. RAMACHANDRA REDDY**

*Department of Commerce,
Sri Venkateswara University,
Tirupati – 517502, India.

**Department of Commerce,
Sri Venkateswara University,
Tirupati – 517502, India.

ABSTRACT

The performance of four mutual funds operated by private sector banks, two each from HDFC and ICICI Prudential Mutual fund are being reported. The period of study being, from the financial year 2002-03 to 2011-12. The funds were compared with S&P CNX Nifty market Index by correlation and standard deviation. The interest offered by State Bank of India on Savings Bank was taken as the risk free return. The statistical Evaluation parameters include, Sharpe's Index, Treynor's Ratio, Jensen's alpha, Fama's Measure and M^2 .

KEYWORDS: *Mutual Funds, Index and Infrastructure.*

INTRODUCTION

The SEBI regulations, 1993 defines a mutual fund as “a fund in the form of a trust by a sponsor, to raise money by the trustees through the sale of units to the public, under one or more schemes, for investing in securities in accordance with these regulations”

A mutual fund is a professionally-managed firm of collective investments that pools money from many investors and invests it in stocks, bonds, short-term money market instruments, and/or other securities. In a mutual fund, the fund manager, who is also known as the portfolio manager, trades the fund's underlying securities, realizing capital gains or losses, and collects the dividend or interest income. The investment proceeds are then passed along to

the individual investors. The value of a share of the mutual fund, known as the net asset value per share (NAV), is calculated daily based on the total value of the fund divided by the number of shares currently issued and outstanding.

Investors, either small or giant would like to invest in mutual funds with a view on profits. A basic knowledge about the different organizations operating mutual funds, the individual past performance of the funds is absolutely necessary. Further, continuous monitoring of the day to day performance of the fund will keep the profile up to date and decision can be taken about continuing in the fund. Hence, analytical evaluation of mutual fund performance becomes absolutely essential. Many researches can be cited based on several characteristics of mutual funds, type, category, fund group. Further work on these lines with enhanced capabilities are always warranted as none of the studies or all of them put together can be termed as an exhaustive account of all the funds for all the times.

In the present study four equity funds two each from (i) HDFC and (ii) ICICI Prudential mutual funds are selected. The selection is based on the long standing and reasonable performance. The portfolio details of the schemes being :

I. HDFC INDEX FUND

Investment Objective: To generate returns that are commensurate with the performance of the Nifty, subject to tracking errors.

Investment Pattern: The net assets of the Plan will be invested predominantly in stocks constituting the S&P CNX Nifty and / or in exchange traded derivatives on the S&P CNX Nifty. This would be done by investing in almost all the stocks comprising the S&P CNX Nifty in approximately the same weightage that they represent in the S&P CNX Nifty Index and / or investing in derivatives including futures contracts and options contracts on the S&P CNX Nifty Index. A small portion of the net assets will be invested in money market instruments permitted by SEBI / RBI including call money market or in alternative investment for the call money market as may be provided by the RBI, to meet the liquidity requirements of the Plan.

ASSET ALLOCATION

Instruments	Normal Allocation %	Risk Profile
Securities covered by the Nifty	95 - 100	Medium to High
Cash & Money Market Instruments, including money at call but excluding Subscription and Redemption Cash Flow	0 - 5	Low to Medium
Subscription Cash Flow is the subscription money in transit before deployment and Redemption Cash Flow is the money kept aside for meeting redemptions.		

Investment Strategy: The Nifty Plan will be managed passively with investments in stocks in a proportion that is as close as possible to the weightages of these stocks in the respective indices.

The investment strategy would revolve around reducing the tracking error to the least possible through regular rebalancing of the portfolio, taking into account the change in weights of stocks in the indices as well as the incremental collections / redemptions from these Plans.

Pursuant to the SEBI Regulations, the respective Plans shall not make any investment in: any unlisted security of an associate or group company of the Sponsor; or any security issued by way of private placement by an associate or group company of the Sponsor; or the listed securities of group companies of the Sponsor which is in excess of 25% of the net assets.

Risk Control: For the Nifty Plan, risks would be the impact cost on securities, the delayed communication of weightage changes by the Index service providers and the net change in assets of each of the Plans, amongst others.

It is proposed to manage the risks by placing limit orders for basket trades and other trades, proactive follow-up with the service providers for daily change in weights in the respective indices as well as monitor daily inflows and outflows to and from the Fund closely.

While these measures are expected to mitigate the above risks to a large extent, there can be no assurance that these risks would be completely eliminated.

Risk control for the actively managed portion of the SENSEX Plus Plan would entail setting limits for single stock and single industry exposures by the Investment committee for this portion, subject to SEBI Regulations.

II. HDFC INFRASTRUCTURE FUND - GROWTH OPTION

Investment Objective: To seek long-term capital appreciation by investing predominantly in equity and equity related securities of companies engaged in or expected to benefit from the growth and development of infrastructure.

INVESTMENT PATTERN

TABLE.1. ASSET ALLOCATION

Instruments	Normal Allocation %	Risk Profile
Instruments of infrastructure / infrastructure related companies	65	Medium High
Equity and Equity lated Instruments of companies other than mentioned above	0	Low Medium
Debt Securities and Money Market Instruments* and Fixed Income Derivative	0	
* Investments in securitised debt shall not normally exceed 30% of the net assets of the Scheme. The Scheme may seek investment opportunity in Foreign Securities (max. 35% of net assets). The Scheme may take derivatives position for hedging		

Position for hedging, portfolio balancing or to undertake any other strategy as permitted under SEBI Regulations from time to time (max. 20% of the net assets) based on the opportunities available subject to SEBI rules.

INVESTMENT STRATEGY: The Scheme shall invest predominantly in equity and equity related securities of companies engaged in or expected to benefit from the growth and development of infrastructure

INVESTMENT STRATEGY: The Scheme shall invest predominantly in equity and equity related securities of companies engaged in or expected to benefit from the growth and development of infrastructure. The Scheme shall invest in the following indicative list of sectors/industries.

- | | | |
|--|---------------------------------------|---|
| 1. Airports | 7. Energy | 12. Engineering |
| 2. Electrical and
Electronic Industries | 8. Housing and
related Industries | 13. Metals/ Mining/
Minerals |
| 3. Construction and
related industries | 9. Industrial
Products | 14. Oil & Gas and allied
industries |
| 4. Industrial Capital goods | 10. Banking and
Financial Services | 15. Power and Power
Equipment |
| 5. Petroleum and related
Related Industries | 11. Cement and
Cement Products | 16. Urban
Infrastructure &
Transportation,
Water, etc. |
| 6. Telecom | | |

The Scheme shall invest across the above-mentioned sectors or other areas of infrastructure as identified by the Fund Manager. It is to be noted that the above list is only indicative and not exhaustive and this could undergo changes based on the future reforms and developments. The Fund Manager may add such other sector/group of industries which broadly satisfy the category of services and infrastructure industries.

The scheme may also invest up to 35% of the fund in non-infrastructure related companies. The Scheme shall invest across all market capitalization.

The balance, if any, will be invested in Debt or Money Market Instruments and Fixed Income Derivative, including securitised debt.

Though every endeavor will be made to achieve the objectives of the Scheme, the AMC/Sponsors/Trustees do not guarantee that the investment objectives of the Scheme will be achieved. No guaranteed returns are being offered under the Scheme. The Scheme may invest

in other schemes managed by the AMC or in the schemes of any other mutual funds, provided it is in conformity with the investment objectives of the Scheme and in terms of the prevailing SEBI Regulations. As per the SEBI Regulations, no investment management fees will be charged for such investments and the aggregate inter scheme investment made by all the schemes of HDFC Mutual Fund or in the schemes of other mutual funds shall not exceed 5% of the net asset value of the HDFC Mutual Fund.

The Scheme may also invest in suitable investment avenues in overseas financial markets for the purpose of diversification, commensurate with the Scheme objectives and subject to necessary stipulations by SEBI / RBI. Towards this end, the Mutual Fund may also appoint overseas investment advisors and other service providers, as and when permissible under the regulations.

Debt Investments: The Scheme will retain the flexibility to invest in the entire range of debt securities and money market instruments. These instruments are more specifically highlighted below: Debt securities (in the form of non-convertible debentures, bonds, secured premium notes, zero interest bonds, deep discount bonds, floating rate bond / notes, securitised debt, pass through certificates, asset backed securities, mortgage backed securities and any other domestic fixed income securities including structured obligations etc.) include, but are not limited to:

Treasury Bills	Government Securities having an unexpired maturity upto 1 year collateral Borrowing & Lending Obligation (CBLO)
Certificate of Deposit	Permitted securities under a repo / reverse repo agreement
Usance Bills	Any other like instruments as may be permitted by RBI / SEBI from time to time
Commercial Bills	

- Debt Obligations of the Government of India, State and local Governments, Government Agencies and statutory bodies (which may or may not carry a state / central government guarantee),
- Securities that have been guaranteed by Government of India and State Governments,
- Securities issued by Corporate Entities (Public / Private sector undertakings),
- Securities issued by Public / Private sector banks and development financial institutions.

Money Market Instruments : Investments will be made through secondary market purchases, initial public offers, other public offers, placements and right offers (including renunciation). The securities could be listed, unlisted, privately placed, secured / unsecured, rated / unrated of any maturity.

The AMC retains the flexibility to invest across all the securities / instruments in debt and money market.

Pursuant to SEBI Circular No. MFD/ CIR/9/120/2000 dated November 24, 2000, the AMC may constitute committee(s) to approve proposals for investments in unrated debt instruments. The AMC Board and the Trustee shall approve the detailed parameters for such investments. The details of such investments would be communicated by the AMC to the Trustee in their periodical reports. It would also be clearly mentioned in the reports, how the parameters have been complied with. However, in case any unrated debt security does not fall under the parameters, the prior approval of Board of AMC and Trustee shall be sought. Investment in debt instruments shall generally have a low risk profile and those in money market instruments shall have an even lower risk profile. The maturity profile of debt instruments will be selected in accordance with the AMC's view regarding current market conditions, interest rate outlook and the stability of ratings. A synoptic view of risks are given hereunder:

Risk Control : Investments made from the net assets of the Scheme would be in accordance with the investment objective of the Scheme and the provisions of the SEBI Regulations. The AMC will strive to achieve the investment objective by way of a judicious portfolio mix comprising of Debt Securities and Money Market Instruments and equity / equity related instruments. Every investment opportunity in Debt Securities and Money Market Instruments would be assessed with regard to credit risk, interest rate risk and liquidity risk.

Credit Risk : A detailed credit evaluation of each investment opportunity will be undertaken. The AMC will utilize ratings of recognized rating agencies as an input in the decision making process. Investments in Debt Securities and Money Market Instruments will usually be in instruments that have been assigned high investment grade ratings by a recognised rating agency. In line with SEBI Circular No. MFD/CIR/9/120/ 2000 dated November 24, 2000, the AMC may constitute committee(s) to approve proposals for investments in unrated instruments. The AMC Board and the Trustee shall approve the detailed parameters for such investments. The details of such investments would be communicated by the AMC to the Trustee in their periodical reports. It would also be clearly mentioned in the reports, how the parameters have been complied with. However, in case any security does not fall under the parameters, the prior approval of Board of AMC and Trustee shall be sought.

Interest Rate Risk : An interest rate scenario analysis would be performed on an on-going basis, considering the impact of the developments on the macro-economic front and the demand and supply of funds. Based on the above analysis, the AMC would manage the investments of the Scheme on a dynamic basis to exploit emerging opportunities in the investment universe and manage risks at all points in time.

Liquidity Risk : The AMC will attempt to reduce liquidity risk by investing in securities that would result in a staggered maturity profile of the portfolio, investment in structured securities that provide easy liquidity and securities that have reasonable secondary market activity. In the event of a requirement to liquidate all or a substantial part of these investments in a very short duration of time, the AMC may not be able to realize the full value of these securities to an adverse impact on the Net Asset Value of the Scheme.

III. ICICI PRUDENTIAL – INDEX FUND - GROWTH OPTION

Objective : To generate capital appreciation through investments in equity related securities in core sectors and associated feeder industries. There are two approaches to reaching your goal: exploring and testing new ground or sticking to the established, long trodden path. The former employs actively investigating and assessing your every move while the later stays within the boundaries of the established.

In the same way, there are two approaches to managing an investor's portfolio. One is active management, which involves choosing sectors and stocks that represent the views of the fund managers, as best suited to meet the portfolio objectives. The other is passive management, which simply means, buying into a market index. ICICI Prudential Index fund , an open-ended index linked growth scheme offers a passive choice to investors, who prefer that their portfolio closely maps the market index, the CNX S&P Nifty index of 50 stocks.

Investment Philosophy :This fund seeks to replicate the CNX S&P Nifty index, by buying the same 50 stocks in the same proportion as they are in the index, hence the fund managers do not take any sector or stock exposure that is different from what is seen on the chosen index. The fund is therefore not actively managed, but passively replicates the index as the objective is to closely track the index.

Investor Profile : This fund is ideal for - Investors with a passive investment philosophy and do not expect out-performance of an index, but simple tracking of the same.

Key Benefits: Long term investment of funds for capital appreciation by replicating S&P CNX Nifty index

IV. ICICI PRUDENTIAL – INFRASTRUCTURE FUND - GROWTH OPTION

Objective : ICICI Prudential Infrastructure Fund seeks to generate capital appreciation and income distribution to unit holders by investing predominantly in equity/equity related securities of the companies belonging to the infrastructure industries and balance in debt securities and money market instruments including call money.

There are two approaches to managing an investor's portfolio. One is active management, which involves choosing sectors and stocks that represent the views of the fund managers, as best suited to meet the portfolio objectives. The other is passive management, which simply means, buying into a market index.

Investment Philosophy: This fund seeks to replicate the CNX S&P Nifty index, by buying the same 50 stocks in the same proportion as they are in the index, hence the fund managers do not take any sector or stock exposure that is different from what is seen on the chosen index. The fund is therefore not actively managed, but passively replicates the index as the objective is to closely track the index.

Investor Profile : This fund is ideal for - Investors with a passive investment philosophy and do not expect out-performance of an index, but simple tracking of the same.

Key Benefits : Long term investment of funds for capital appreciation by replicating S&P CNX Nifty index.

TABLE.2. FUND FEATURE COMPARISON

	HDFC		ICICI Prudential		
	Index - Nifty Plan	Infrastructure (G)	Index (G)	Infrastructure (G)	
Fund Class	Index	Infrastructure	Index	Infrastructure	
Scheme Asset ₹. cr	81.00	562.00	87.00	1287.00	
Inception	Jul 10, 2002	Feb 21, 2008	Feb 15, 2002	Aug 16, 2005	
Benchmark	S&P CNX Nifty	S&P CNX 500	S&P CNX Nifty		
Minimum Investment	₹.5000	₹,5000	₹.5000	₹.5000	
AMC Asset 30-6-2012	₹.92,624.52 (cr)	₹92,624.52(cr)	₹73,049.66(cr)	₹73,049.66(cr)	
NAV Details	Latest (₹./Unit)14-8-2012	46.5331	9.6240	50.508	25.2100
	52 week High 21.2.2012	48.347	10.987	52.372	27.620
	Low 19.12.2012	39.893	8.140	43.492	22.010
Performance Returns as on Aug 14, 12					
3 Months	9.7%	5.0%	9.4%	9.1%	
6 Months	-2.5%	-10.6%	-2.3%	-7.1%	
1 Year	6.4%	-8.8%	7.0%	-4.2%	
2 Years	-0.7%	-12.6%	0.2%	-8.5%	
3 Years	6.4%	3.0%	7.5%	-0.1%	
5 Years	2.8%	-	6.2%	3.4%	
Portfolio					
Top 5 holdings	ITC, Reliance, ICICI Bank, Infosys, HDFC Bank	ICICI Bank, Bank of Baroda, BPCL, SBI, Federal Bank	ITC, Reliance, Infosys, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank	Reliance, ONGC, Bharti Airtel, HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank	
Weightage	Top 5 holdings				
	35%	37.84%	29.21%	34.74%	
Top 3 Sectors	Banking/ Finance, Oil & Gas, Technology	Banking/Finance, Oil & Gas, Engineering	Banking/Finance, Technology, Oil & Gas	Banking/Finance, Oil & Gas, Utilities	
Weightage	Top 3 sectors				
	51.68%	60.22%	43.39%	55.15%	
Management & Fees	Entry Load	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Exit Load	1.00%	1.00%	0.25%	1.00%
For Redemption within		30 days	1 year	1 year	1 year

METHODOLOGY

To make the study comprehensive the period of study was chosen from the financial year 2002-03, which corresponds to the earliest days of the schemes, to the financial year 2011-12. The NAV values of the selected schemes were compiled on monthly basis and compounded to annual returns. (R_p). Similarly the annual returns of the market index, S&P CNX Nifty (R_M) were also obtained. The risk free index (R_F) was taken as the Savings Bank Account Interest Rate offered by state Bank of India, which is 4% for the years 2002 and 2012 and 3.2% for the rest of the years, corresponding to 0.330 and 0.292% respectively.

The statistical evaluation parameters, correlation, standard deviation (σ), Treynor's Index (T_f), Sharpe's Index (S_i), Jensen's Alpha (α_j), Fama's Measure (F_p) and M^2 Measure were computed and the funds were appraised from these observations.

METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The NAV values used in the study are obtained from AMFI's website, which in turn is supplied by the members. Members in turn have not followed any uniform rule in its computation due to the flexibilities offered under SEBI regulations.
2. Initially all mutual fund schemes were directly linked to stock market. In the recent 2 years numerous schemes which are independent of stock market (debt & money market funds) are introduced and such schemes' returns need not have correlation with index, and the index is not adjusted for dividends.
3. Banks are free to accept deposits at any interest within the ceilings fixed by Reserve Bank of India and interest rates can vary from client to client. Hence there can be an inaccuracy in the risk-free rates.
4. The analysis is not free from the limitations of non-identical time periods and unequal sample observations.
5. The study excludes the effect of entry and exit loads of the mutual funds.

RESULTS

The R_p values and the corresponding R_M values and the σ values are included in tables 3.a and 3.b for comparison and correlation. Fig.1 represents the comparison of the NAV.

TABLE.3.A. PORTFOLIO RETURN, MARKET RETURN, AND CORRELATION COEFFICIENT OF THE SELECTED SCHEMES

Fund ↓Year	R_p				R_M
	HDFC		ICICI Prudential		S&P CNX Nifty
	Index	Infrastructure	Index	Infrastructure	
2011-12	-0.0083	-0.0113	-0.0001	-0.0071	-1.2000
2010-11	0.0028	-0.0016	0.0029	0.0342	0.5800
2009-10	0.0344	0.0064	0.0344	-0.0347	0.0447
2008-09	-0.0364	-0.0336	-0.0320	0.0276	-0.038
2007-08	0.0166		0.0052	0.0050	0.0179
2006-07	-0.0364		0.0165	0.0404	0.0100
2005-06	0.0349		-0.0186		0.0973
2004-05	0.0016		0.0393		0.0166
2003-04	0.0417		0.0041		0.0512
2002-03	-0.0045		0.0160		0.0705
$Corr_{(R_p, R_M)}$	0.8590	0.9409	0.8712	0.1505	

TABLE.3.B. STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE SELECTED SCHEMES

Fund ↓Year	σ_p				σ_M
	HDFC		ICICI Prudential		S&P CNX Nifty
	Index	Infrastructure	Index	Infrastructure	
2011-12	0.06466	0.08629	0.06460	0.04761	0.0666
2010-11	0.05534	0.05294	0.05535	0.06297	0.0602
2009-10	0.08680	0.07419	0.08679	0.13733	0.0973
2008-09	0.11611	0.10252	0.12126	0.09113	0.1103
2007-08	0.08949		0.08306	0.07837	0.9084
2006-07	0.11611		0.08899	0.06973	0.6291
2005-06	0.06269		0.06043		0.0647
2004-05	0.06543		0.07359		0.0709
2003-04	0.07066		0.06927		0.0705
2002-03	0.05711		0.05787		0.1110

FIG.1. NAV COMPARISON: S&P CNX NIFTY AND THE SELECTED FUNDS

STATISTICAL EVALUATION

Fund	Year	S_t	T_f	α_j	F_p	M^2
HDFC Index	2011-12	-5.23	-0.3788	-0.0361	-0.0100	0.6634
	2010-11	-5.55	-0.4251	-0.0837	-0.3752	-0.3221
	2009-10	-2.97	-0.3232	-0.0921	-0.0314	0.6663
	2008-09	-2.83	-3.5291	-0.2977	0.0171	0.7214
	2007-08	-3.08	-0.3257	-0.0383	-0.2750	0.7089
	2006-07	-2.83	2.6540	-0.3633	5.2990	0.8310
	2005-06	-4.10	-0.2927	-1.1354	0.2753	0.6908
	2004-05	-4.44	-0.3510	-1.1175	0.0539	0.6737
2003-04	-3.54	2.0228	-0.1266	3.7591	0.6991	

	2002-03	-5.86	0.0665	-2.0530	-0.0232	0.6611
	Overall	-4.043	-0.0882	-0.5343	0.8689	0.5993
HDFC Infrastructure	2011-12	-3.96	1.0216	-0.4556	-0.0190	0.0103
	2010-11	-5.23	-0.3588	-0.0442	-0.0236	0.0031
	2009-10	-3.85	-1.4131	-0.2436	-0.2515	0.5785
	2008-09	-3.18	-4.9027	-0.3037	-0.0399	0.6856
	Overall	-4.055	-1.4133	-0.2618	-0.0835	0.3194
ICICI Prudential Index	2011-12	-5.11	-0.4052	-0.0514	-0.0101	1.7031
	2010-11	-5.22	-0.3587	-0.0561	-0.0235	0.6795
	2009-10	-2.97	-0.1514	0.1807	-0.0372	0.6663
	2008-09	-2.67	-0.1207	0.5458	0.0320	0.7374
	2007-08	-3.45	-1.5528	-0.2338	-0.0246	0.6675
	2006-07	-3.10	-1.8120	-0.2326	0.1142	0.8070
	2005-06	-1.06	-6.2120	-2.5081	-0.0205	0.6260
	2004-05	-3.43	-0.2399	0.0135	0.0096	0.7478
	2003-04	-4.16	-4.3782	-1.9072	-0.0513	0.655605
	2002-03	-5.43	-1.0103	-1.2691	-1.8537	0.9181
	Overall	-3.66	-1.6241	-0.5518	-0.1865	0.8208
ICICI Prudential Infrastructure	2011-12	-3.93	-0.4211	-0.0575	0.0953	-6.2351
	2010-11	-6.28	-0.4475	-0.0992	-0.0627	0.6158
	2009-10	-4.09	-0.2094	0.0597	-0.0979	0.5566

	2008-09	-2.38	-0.1090	0.6524	0.0798	0.7605
	2007-08	-2.90	0.6826	-0.3669	0.0008	0.7187
	2006-07	-3.66	-0.2951	-0.0127	0.0705	0.7618
	2005-06	-0.86	-0.2899	-1.6942	0.0195	0.7286
	Overall	-3.44	-0.1556	-0.2169	0.0150	-0.2990

ANALYSIS

The standard deviation is an indicator of the risk associated with a fund and hence the performance of a fund with least standard deviation speaks about its performance. In the present instance almost all the cases the standard deviation of the funds is comparable to the market values except in a few cases such as HDFC Equity fund in 2008-09 and 2006-07.

The correlation of the performance compared to the market can be considered as excellent for HDFC Infrastructure fund and good for HDFC Index and ICICI Index funds, where as it was poor for ICICI Infrastructure fund.

The superiority of the Sharpe ratio over the Treynor ratio is, it considers the point whether investors are reasonably rewarded for the total risk in comparison to the market. A mutual fund scheme with a relatively large unique risk may outperform the market in Treynor's index and may under perform the market in Sharpe ratio. A mutual fund scheme with large Treynor ratio and low Sharpe ratio can be concluded to have relatively larger Nothing much can be said about the funds performance based on sharpe's Index as all the values being negative speaks for themselves. Same is the case with the Treynor's Index. None of the funds have appositive Alpha. HDFC Index fund has a positive F_p . A positive value for F_p indicates that the fund earned returns higher than expected returns and lies above CML, and a negative value indicates that the fund earned returns less than expected returns and lies below CML. The purpose of performance evaluation is that it should be in a position to identify the mistakes and suggest a direction for the correction. A comparison of Sharpe's and Treynor's ratios will help the fund managers to correct their actions from risk angle and comparison of Jensen's and Fama's measures will help from return angle.

ICICI Prudential Index fund has the highest M^2 value.

CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, though no foolproof definite conclusion could be drawn from the present data keeping in view the long term nature of the funds, the work is clearly indicative, theoretical and suggests the continuous monitoring of these index and infrastructure funds.

REFERENCES

1. Eugene Fama, "Components of Investment Performance", *Journal of Finance*, 27, (June 1972), pp. 551-567
2. Gupta L.C, "Indian share owners: A survey", *Society for Capital Market Research and development*, 1991, p.92.
3. Jack L. Treynor, "How to rate Management of Investment Funds", *Harvard Business Review*, 43, No.1, (January-February, 1965), pp. 63-75.
4. Jagric, T., Podobnik, B., Sebastian, S. and Jagrick, V., *South-Eastern Europe Journal of Economics*, 2 (2007) 233-244. William F. Sharpe, "Mutual Fund Performance", *Journal of Business*, 39, No.1, (January 1966), pp. 119-138.
5. Michael C. Jensen, "The Performance of Mutual Funds in the period 1945-1964", *Journal of Finance*, 23, No.2, (May 1968), pp. 389-416.
6. "Mutual Fund Year Book-2012", Joint Publication of Association of Mutual funds in India
7. Nimalthasan, B., Kumar Gandhi, R., EXCEL, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Management Studies*, 2,3, 2012.
8. Sharpe W.F, "A simplified Model for Portfolio Analysis", *Management science* 9. (January 1963), pp.277-293.
9. Shah Ajay and Thomas Susan, "Performance Evaluation of Professional Portfolio Management in India", *Center for Monitoring Indian Economy*, (working paper) April, 1994.
10. Singh, K.S., Singh, K.B, and Singh, A., *Asian Journal of Research in Banking and Finance*, 2 (2012) 59.

11. UTI Institute of Capital Markets, 2001, pp. 29-139.
12. William F. Sharpe, "Mutual Fund Performance", Journal of Business, 39, No.1, (January 1966), pp. 119-138.

